

Structure and chemistry of printed contacts on solar cells: correlative AFM, Kelvin probe and SEM analysis with RGB color-coding

In modern silicon-based and other solar cells, electrical contacts are the key components that can enhance or limit the performance. Correlated AFM-in-SEM analysis can enable direct insight into structural, electronic and chemical interactions at the solar cell contact interface.

AFM-in-SEM data enabled direct *in-situ* correlation between AFM topography, Kelvin probe map (KPFM), secondary (SE) and back scattered (BSE) electron intensity maps across the printed contact on silicon solar cell. Structural and work function profiles, material composition and diffusion were thereby observed at the contact interface. The correlated data revealed a localized damage of the pn-junction.

Figure 1: SEM image of the solar cell printed contact cross-section with the approaching AFM tip. Inset: photograph of the solar cell sample in LiteScope AFM placed inside EVO 10 SEM for the CPEM analysis.

Figure 2: LiteScope AFM topography, KPFM surface workfunction map, SE and BSE images across the the printed contact on solar cell. Below are 3D KPFM image (scale 0.5 eV) and 3D color-coded CPEM image (SE-red, BSE-cyan) based on the above data correlation.

Figure 3: RGB SEM image of a solar cell contact cross-section created using 5 kV SE, 10 kV SE and 10 kV BSE images.

Correlated RGB SEM image was assembled from three grayscale intensity images obtained in the same contact region under different regimes (SE/BSE) and parameters (acceleration voltage). In the separate images, different material properties and interactions are hard to distinguish. In the correlated SEM image, the glass frit, aluminum paste, p-type Si emitter and n-type Si wafer give rise to different colors and can be directly identified. Moreover, diffused Al (green color) into the n-type Si (grey color) can be clearly recognized (red rectangle). By linking to AFM morphology, presence of such regions was identified as the main reason of malfunction of this solar cell type.

